

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Dulcitol by Chloramine-T

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Kinetics of oxidation of dulcitol by chloramine-T in alkaline media has been investigated. A brief initial induction period has been observed after which the reaction shows a first order dependence each in [chloramine-T], [dulcitol] and $[\text{OH}^-]$. The effect of added neutral salts on the reaction rate is negligible. Energy of activation is observed to be 33.3 Kcal/mole for the reaction. A plausible mechanism consistent to the experimental data has been proposed.

THE kinetics of oxidation of several alcohols by chloramine-T in acidic media has been investigated by Mushran *et al*¹⁻³. Natarajan and Thiagarajan⁴ have also studied the oxidation of secondary alcohols in acidic media. Recently Mahadevappa and Naidu have also studied the chloraminometric oxidation of allyl alcohol^{5,6} and cinnamyl alcohol⁷. The oxidation of polyhydric alcohols by chloramine-T has not been studied so far. In this communication, the study of kinetics of oxidation of dulcitol in alkaline media is made. The progress of reaction in neutral or acidic media is found too slow to be studied kinetically.

Experimental

Aqueous solution of dulcitol (E. Merck) was prepared. Stock solutions of chloramine-T (E. Merck) and sodium hydroxide (A.R.) were prepared. The solutions were stored in black coated bottles to prevent photochemical influences⁸. All other chemicals viz. KNO_3 , K_2SO_4 , NaNO_3 and Na_2SO_4 were of analytical grade. Double-distilled water was always used for the preparation and dilution of the solutions throughout the course of reaction.

Reactants were brought to thermostatic temperature ($+0.1^\circ$) and allowed the reaction mixture to equilibrate for 30 minutes after which an appropriate amount of chloramine-T was added to initiate the reaction. The kinetics was followed by estimating chloramine-T iodometrically in aliquot portion of the reaction mixture withdrawn after definite time intervals.

Results

(a) Stoichiometry :

Reaction mixtures containing excess of chloramine-T over dulcitol were allowed to equilibrate at 40° in respective sodium hydroxide concentration. The results showed that one mole of dulcitol was oxidised by three moles of chloramine-T forming galactonic acid which was examined by positive spot test. Thus the stoichiometric equation for the reaction may be represented as :

(b) Chloramine-T dependence :

The oxidation of dulcitol by chloramine-T was investigated in highly alkaline media. It was observed that the reaction shows a brief initial induction period after which first order dependence on chloramine-T was observed. Pseudo first order rate constants (k_1) were calculated from the slopes of \log [chloramine-T]—time plots of several initial concentrations of chloramine-T. A fairly constant value $0.58 + 0.03 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ was obtained.

(c) [Dulcitol] dependence :

The dependence with respect to dulcitol was determined by carrying out the kinetic runs with its different concentrations and keeping the concentrations of other reactants constant. A linear increase in first order rate constants calculated from $k_2 = k_1/[\text{dulcitol}]$ gave concordant values establishing a first order dependence in dulcitol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DULCITOL CONCENTRATION ON REACTION RATE

[Dulcitol] $\times 10^2 M$	$k_1 \times 10^2 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_1/[\text{dulcitol}] \text{ min}^{-1}$ mole ⁻¹
0.5	0.30	0.60
0.6	0.37	0.61
0.7	0.42	0.60
0.8	0.47	0.59
0.9	0.53	0.59
1.0	0.57	0.57
1.1	0.62	0.56
1.2	0.70	0.58

(d) [NaOH] dependence :

The rate of oxidation of dulcitol by chloramine-T was found to be enough sensitive to the change in OH^- ion concentration. Influence of NaOH concentration variation on reaction rate was studied by taking fixed concentrations of oxidant and substrate and varying the concentration of NaOH.

First order dependence in NaOH was established by getting concordant values of k_1 $[\text{NaOH}]$ for a wide range of NaOH concentration (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[\text{NaOH}]$ ON REACTION RATE

$[\text{Chloramine-T}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{Dulcitol}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, temp. = 35°C	$k_2 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_1 / [\text{NaOH}] \text{ min}^{-1}$ mole $^{-1}$
4.0	0.35	0.88
6.0	0.57	0.95
8.0	0.74	0.92
10.0	0.90	0.90
12.0	1.07	0.89
14.0	1.26	0.90
16.0	1.47	0.92
18.0	1.66	0.92

(e) Rate dependence on ionic strength :

The effect of added neutral salts was found to be negligible on the reaction rate (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH

$[\text{Chloramine-T}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{Dulcitol}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, temp. = 35°C .	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$			
$[\text{Salt}] \times 10^3 M$	KNO_3	K_2SO_4	NaNO_3	Na_2SO_4
2.0	0.59	0.54	0.53	0.58
4.0	0.57	0.55	0.54	0.53
6.0	0.55	0.52	0.55	0.53

(f) Temperature dependence :

Kinetic runs were carried out at four different temperatures to calculate the energy of activation for the reaction. The pseudo first order rate constants at different temperatures are summarised in Table 4.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE

$[\text{Chloramine-T}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{Dulcitol}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.				
Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	32.5	35	37.5	40
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.35	0.57	0.80	1.3

The energy of activation was calculated from the slope of Arrhenius plot which was found to be 33.3 Kcal/mole.

Discussion

Dulcitol is rapidly converted into galactose by alkaline chloramine-T. Hence the kinetics of oxidation of dulcitol is related to the kinetics of oxidation of galactose. The experimental findings reveal that the reaction followed a first order dependence each in $[\text{chloramine-T}]$, $[\text{dulcitol}]$ and $[\text{NaOH}]$. The effect of added neutral salts was found to be insignificant which leads to the conclusion that the reaction

takes place between neutral molecules or between an ion and a neutral molecule. The following mechanism has been proposed which has been found in consonance with the experimental results.

Aqueous solution of chloramine-T hydrolyses to *p*-toluene sulphochloramide and sodium hydroxide.

Under experimental condition (at high alkali concentration) equilibrium almost lies towards left i.e. almost all the chloramine-T is in unhydrolysed form which itself should be an effective species. Direct dependence on $[\text{NaOH}]$ also supports this fact.

Dulcitol is fast converted into galactose.

Galactose exists in two anomeric forms which are in equilibrium in aqueous solution. The conformations of these are

β -anomer is more reactive and the anion of this β -anomer exists in alkaline aqueous medium⁹⁻¹¹.

This anion reacts with chloramine-T (oxidising species) itself in a slow step to form an intermediate which further interacts in a fast step with chloramine-T to generate products. Equations are as under :

Applying steady galactonic acid anion state

assumption to the intermediates and assuming that water is in large excess and $k-1 [H_2O] \gg k_2 [\text{chloramine-T}]$ the rate of disappearance of chloramine-T is given by

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [\text{chloramine-T}] = k_1 [\text{chloramine-T}] [\text{galactose}] [\text{OH}^-]$$

where $k_1 = \frac{2k_1 k_2}{k-1 [H_2O]}$

Since dulcitol is converted into an equivalent amount of galactose in a fast step.

$$[\text{dulcitol}] = [\text{galactose}]$$

Thus the rate law is

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [\text{chloramine-T}] = k_1 [\text{chloramine-T}] [\text{dulcitol}] [\text{OH}^-]$$

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